

Supplemental Materials for:

Breaking the Mirror: How Conventional Construction Firms Embrace Industrialized Construction

This document provides supplemental materials for the article “Breaking the Mirror: How Conventional Construction Firms Embrace Industrialized Construction”. It includes details on variable scaling, the empirical characterization (Appendix 1), and robustness and sensitivity analyses of the technical typology (Appendix 2).

Appendix 1. Variable scaling and empirical firm characterization

Appendix 1 details the scaling procedures applied to the original variables to ensure comparability prior to conducting the organizational analysis anchored in technical types (Table S-1). It also includes a comprehensive table presenting the normalized values and the allocation of each case across the analytical dimensions (Table S-2).

Table S-1. Original variables scaling

Ts1	Ts2	Os1 & Os4	Os2 & Os5	Os3 & Os6	Os7	Os8
Transferring activities to supply chain	Predefinition	Ownership integration	Multi-project organization	Operational integration	Intra-project IT-based integration	Across-project IT-based integration
0.00 - (i) NS-NS/2D-PA	0.00 - (i) DTO _{ED}	0.00 – (i) Market	0.00 – (i) Comp	0.00 – (i) Low	0.00 – (i) Isolated	0.00 – (i) No integration
0.25 - (ii) NS-S/1D/2D-SA+NS-NS/2D-PA	0.25 - (ii) ATO _{1ED}					
0.30 - (iii) NS-S/1D/2D-SA + NS-NS/3D-PA						
0.50 - (iv) S-S-1D/2D-SA+NS-NS/2D-PA	0.50 - (iii) ATO _{2ED}	0.50 – (ii) Partial	0.50 – (ii) I-Coop	0.50 – (ii) Partial	0.50 – (ii) Aggregated	0.50 – (ii) Ad hoc
0.55 - (v) S-S-1D/2D-SA+NS-NS/3D-PA						
0.75 - (vi) S-S/2D-PA	0.75 - (iv) ATO _{3ED}					
1.00 - (vii) S-S/3D-PA	1.00 - (v) ATO _{4ED}	1.00 - (iii) In-house	1.00 – (iii) F-Coop	1.00 - (iii) Advanced	1.00 – (iii) Integrated	1.00 - (iii) IK-Platform

* For the dimension Impact on the production line, to better reflect the conceptual proximity between certain adoption strategies, smaller differences were assigned between subcategories sharing the same primary approach (e.g., SC-1D/2D-SA combined with either NS-2D-PA or NS-3D-PA) than between categories representing fundamentally different primary approaches (e.g., SC-1D/2D-SA versus SS-1D/2D-SA). This scaling captures the fact that, while variations exist within a given primary approach, they are less substantial than the differences observed between distinct primary approaches.

Table S-2. Empirical firm characterization

		Ts1	Ts2	Os1	Os2	Os3	Os4	Os5	Os6	Os7	Os8
Case	Country	Transferring activities to supply chain	Predef	Ownership integration	Multi-project organization	Operational integration	Ownership integration	Multi-project organization	Operational integration	Intra-project IT-based integration	Across-project IT-based integration
1.1	Chile	0.25	0.25	0	0.5	0.5	0	0.00	0	0.5	0.5
1.2	Chile	0.30	0.75	0.5	1	1	0.5	0.50	1	0.5	1
1.3a	Chile	0.30	0.75	1	1	1	0	0.00	0	1	1
1.3b	Chile	0.30	0.75	0	0.5	1	0	0.00	0	1	1
1.4	Chile	0.30	0.00	1	1	0.5	0	0.00	0	0.5	0
1.5	Chile	0.00	0.50	1	1	0.5	0	0.00	0	1	0.5
1.6	Chile	0.30	0.25	0.5	1	0.5	0	0.00	0	0.5	0.5
1.7	Chile	0.25	0.00	1	1	0.5	0	0.00	0	0.5	0
1.8	Chile	0.00	0.00	0.5	1	0.5	0	0.00	0	0.5	0.5
1.9	Chile	0.25	0.00	0.5	1	0.5	0	0.00	0	0.5	0
1.10	Chile	0.30	0.25	0.5	1	0.5	0	0.00	0	1	0
1.11	Chile	0.25	0.50	0.5	1	0.5	0	0.00	0	0.5	0.5
1.12	Chile	0.00	0.25	0	0.5	0.5	0	0.00	0	0.5	0.5
2.1a	Spain	0.55	0.25	0	0.5	0	0	1.00	0	0.5	1
2.1b	Spain	0.75	0.00	0	0.5	1	0	0.00	1	0.5	0
2.2a	Spain	0.50	0.25	1	1	0.5	0.5	0.50	1	0.5	1
2.2b	Spain	0.50	0.00	0	0	0	0.5	0.50	0	0	0
2.3	Spain	0.50	0.00	0	0	0	0	0.00	0	0	0
2.4	Spain	0.30	1.00	1	1	1	0	1.00	1	1	1
2.5	Spain	0.75	0.00	0	0.5	0.5	0	0.00	0.5	0.5	0
2.6	Spain	1.00	0.00	0	0.5	1	1	1.00	1	0.5	1
2.7	Spain	0.50	0.75	0	0.5	1	0	1.00	0.5	1	1
2.8	Spain	0.50	0.00	0.5	1	0	0	0.00	0	1	0
2.9	Spain	0.30	0.00	0	0	0	0	0.00	0	0	0
2.10	Spain	0.50	0.00	0	0	0.5	0.5	0.50	0.5	1	1
2.11	Spain	0.75	0.00	0	0	0.5	1	1.00	1	0	1
2.12	Spain	0.75	0.00	0	0	1	0	0.00	0.5	0.5	0
3.1	UK	0.30	1.00	1	1	1	0.5	0.50	0.5	0.5	1
3.2	UK	0.55	0.75	0	0	0	0	0.50	0	1	1
3.3	UK	0.50	0.00	1	1	0.5	0	0.00	0	1	0.5
3.4	UK	0.55	0.75	1	1	1	0	1.00	0	1	1
3.5	UK	0.55	0.75	0	0.5	1	0	1.00	0.5	1	1

Appendix 2. Robustness assessment via sensitivity analysis for technical typology

Appendix 2 assesses the robustness of the technical typology constructed from the Ts1 and Ts2 dimensions. Specifically, it reports (i) the base specification used to assign observations to quadrants and technical types (Table S-3), and (ii) a sensitivity analysis under plausible alternative specifications (e.g., alternative thresholds for the Ts2 split) to make the stability of the classification transparent (Table S-4). For each alternative specification, we document any resulting reassignments and summarize their implications for the overall interpretation of the typology.

Table S-3. Base specification (S0): decision rules for assigning observations to quadrants and technical types

Inputs. Each observation is characterized by: (i) **Ts1**, coded as an observed configuration of activity transfer to the supply chain (including single-system and multi-system cases with *primary* and *secondary* approaches); and (ii) **Ts2**, coded as ATO_{ED} , $ATO1_{ED}$, $ATO2_{ED}$, $ATO3_{ED}$, or $ATO4_{ED}$.

Panel A. Quadrant assignment (S0)

Dimension	Operational rule (S0)
Ts1 (vertical axis)	High Ts1 = systematic approaches (S-S), defined by the presence of explicit compatibility rules. Low Ts1 = non-systematic approaches (NS-S and NS-NS).
Ts2 (horizontal axis)	High Ts2 $\geq ATO2_{ED}$ ($ATO2_{ED}$, $ATO3_{ED}$, $ATO4_{ED}$), i.e., predefinition that consolidates reusable solutions at least at the component level. Low Ts2 = $ATO_{ED} - ATO1_{ED}$ (codes/standards or guiding templates that inform design without materializing reusable solutions).

Resulting quadrants

- **Quadrant I (QI):** High Ts1 & High Ts2
- **Quadrant II (QII):** High Ts1 & Low Ts2
- **Quadrant III (QIII):** Low Ts1 & Low Ts2
- **Quadrant IV (QIV):** Low Ts1 & High Ts2

Panel B. Type assignment (S0)

Location in the Ts1×Ts2 space	Type assignment rule
QI	Ts-F
QIII	Ts-A
QII	Subtyping by the predominant Ts1 transfer mechanism: Ts-D when the systematic approach relies primarily on 1D/2D sub-assemblies (1D/2D-SA); Ts-E when it relies primarily on 2D/3D pre-assemblies (2D-PA and/or 3D-PA).
QIV	Subtyping by the aggregation level of Ts2: Ts-B if $Ts2 = ATO2_{ED}$ (predefinition at the level of individual elements); Ts-C if $Ts2 \in \{ATO3_{ED}, ATO4_{ED}\}$ (predefinition at the level of spaces or functional units).

Note. For multi-system Ts1 observations (a *primary* and a *secondary* approach), quadrant and subtype assignment is determined by the primary approach; the secondary approach is retained as contextual information.

Table S-4. Sensitivity analysis of the technical typology under alternative plausible specifications.

Panel A. Alternative specifications

Specification	Change relative to S0	Rationale
S1 (Ts2 stricter cut)	Re-define High Ts2 = ATO3 _{ED} -ATO4 _{ED} only; treat ATO2 _{ED} as not-high (i.e., it no longer qualifies for High Ts2).	Tests whether treating “predefinition at component level” (ATO2 _{ED}) as High Ts2 is pivotal; addresses boundary sensitivity on the horizontal axis.
S2 (QII subtype rule sensitive to secondary 3D)	In QII only, reassign observations with Ts1 category v (S-S/1D/2D-SA + NS-NS/3D-PA) to Ts-E instead of Ts-D (secondary 3D presence treated as subtype-relevant).	Tests sensitivity of intra-quadrant subtyping where primary 1D/2D-SA coexists with a 3D-PA secondary approach.

Panel B. Impact on assignment

Specification	# observations changing quadrant	# observations changing subtype only	Observation IDs affected
S1	2 (6.25%)	0 (0.00%)	1.5, 1.11
S2	0 (0.00%)	1 (3.13%)	2.1a

Note: Changes concentrate on boundary observations driven by alternative thresholding (ATO2_{ED}) or a secondary-based subtyping convention in multi-system cases; quadrant assignment remains stable except under the stricter Ts2 cut.